

Using Foreign Experience in Hr Management in Organizations

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Abstract: This article examines the experience of foreign countries in personnel management in organizations such as America, Japan and European countries. The main tasks of personnel management in the organization are defined. Based on the study of foreign experience, the elements that should be paid attention to when managing personnel in the country are analyzed.

Keywords: personnel, management, systematicity, human resources, motivation, method, organization, foreign experience, efficiency.

Introduction. Nowadays, no one doubts that the most important resource of any enterprise is its employees. However, not all managers understand how difficult it is to manage this resource. The success of any enterprise depends on how effective the work of employees is. The task of managers is to use the capabilities of personnel as effectively as possible. No matter how strong the decisions of managers are, the effect from them can be obtained only when they are successfully implemented in the work of the employees of the enterprise.

Personnel management is a specific management function in which the main object is a person who is part of a certain social group. The foundation of modern personnel management theory is the concept of complex personality development, as well as the basic theory of human relations, based on the principles of employee motivation and administrative management methods.

Personnel management includes the following types of management activities:

- ✓ formation of personnel strategy;
- ✓ selection of employees corresponding to the company's development strategy;
- ✓ encouragement of collective interaction aimed at the company's development;
- ✓ stimulation of individual activity of staff members in accordance with its quality;
- ✓ creation of a favorable socio-psychological climate in the organization.

The purpose of personnel management is to form such a qualitative and quantitative composition that will ensure the competitiveness and strategic development of the company, increase the efficiency of production and labor, achieve the highest possible level of profit, and ensure high social efficiency of personnel functioning. Effective achievement of the company's goals requires solving the following tasks:

- ✓ meeting the need for labor of the required quantity and skill level;

- ✓ maintaining an optimal balance between the organizational and technical structure of the company's production and labor potential;
- ✓ maximizing and effectively using the potential of individual employees and the entire staff as a whole;
- ✓ creating conditions for highly productive labor, the proper degree of its organization, motivation, self-discipline, developing the habit of interaction and cooperation among team members;
- ✓ retaining employees on the company's staff, forming a stable team as a condition for the payback of resources spent on personnel;
- ✓ ensuring that the needs and interests of employees are met in terms of the content of work, its conditions, type of employment, opportunities for professional, qualification and career growth;
- ✓ coordinating production and social objectives (balancing the interests of the company and staff members, economic and social efficiency).

The personnel management system is a set of techniques, methods, and technologies for organizing work with personnel. According to systems theory, any system is a set of elements that can be considered as independent systems with their own goals and objectives. The company's personnel management system cannot be isolated from the company's management system as a whole, since it covers not only the departments directly involved in working with personnel, but also managers at all levels of the organization.

Studying the experience of foreign companies allows us to formulate the key goal of the personnel management system: providing the company with personnel, their effective use, professional and social development. It is advisable to study foreign experience in implementing the tasks set in the field of personnel management in the organization. In the foreign theory of personnel management, American, Japanese, and European approaches are compared. These approaches have certain distinctive features.

The American approach to personnel management is based on a strict management organization. It is characterized by the individual nature of decision-making and individual responsibility. The individual control of the manager is clearly expressed, while the control procedure is clearly formalized. The manager is a professional, a business career is based on personal achievements. American companies use traditional principles of recruitment, the emphasis is on the presence of professional skills and abilities. The leading selection criteria are education, practical experience, and the ability to work in a team. The emphasis is on training highly specialized managers.

After hiring, an induction procedure is carried out, the employee is introduced to his/her functions and responsibilities in accordance with the job description, there is no introduction to the corporate culture of the company as a whole. Through training outside of working hours, promotion is possible. The labor incentive system is not an effective way of motivation, incentives increase as the employee advances up the career ladder. The payment system is not flexible enough.

The main features of management in an American company:

- Functionality, which means clearly assigned job responsibilities for an employee. The principle: focus on what you do best; it doesn't matter what you are, it matters what you can do as a specialist.
- The manager's task is to reveal the employee's creative potential. Encouragement of new ideas.
- Mandatory retraining and continuous learning.

- Management by objectives. Dismemberment of any task, where the solution is associated with a set of heterogeneous knowledge. A clear algorithm for achieving.
- Implementation of opposite trends: a rigid functional approach (for example, a conveyor system) and a large number of leaders and creative individuals, decentralization and centralization, rigidity in defending one's interests and flexibility in implementation.
- Career growth occurs strictly within the framework of professional specialization.
- Developed corporate culture.
- Management is considered a strong competitive advantage.

The Japanese approach to personnel management is quite flexible. Flexibility is demonstrated in collective decision-making based on unanimity, group-oriented management, remuneration based on group performance indicators, and collective responsibility. The key performance indicator in the company is not profit, but quality. Informal personal relationships with subordinates are allowed in the team, and the main quality of a manager is the ability to coordinate actions and control.

The management supports the employees' suggestions for improving the activity; if the suggestion is worthwhile, the middle manager passes it on to the senior management.

In Japan, a system of "lifetime employment" (guaranteed employment) is adopted in large companies. After completing their studies, a graduate is hired and works until retirement. A feature of personnel management in the Japanese approach is the system of payment and career advancement "by seniority". Salary depends on age and length of service in the company, this encourages working in the company for a long time.

Japanese companies have a well-developed system of personnel training and professional development. Personnel rotation is used, employees can be transferred to another department, to another position in order to acquire new skills and abilities. This is the basis for personnel career planning. The Japanese approach is special, unlike any other country. Personnel management methods in Japan reflect the established traditions of the national character of the country.

Japanese companies use a whole system of non-material (moral) incentives for good employees: promotion; bonuses, valuable gifts; issuance of author's certificates; holding special meetings where high-quality work of an employee is noted; providing benefits for purchasing company shares; paid trips to the customer's enterprises (including in other countries); publication of special articles in the company's internal publication (press); organizing a trip out of town for employees with their families at the company's expense; organizing joint lunches for employees with the company's management; specially designated places for parking cars, etc. The specifics of Japanese management, which takes into account the psychology of people and their social status and has allowed them to achieve unusual success in industry, contributed to the improvement of traditional methods of personnel management in other countries with developed economies.

The European approach to personnel management is close to the American approach, since Japan is an Eastern country. For example, if we take Germany, then the following features of personnel management are typical for it. This is the allocation of a specialized HR service, which deals with all issues of personnel management. Employees from the internal reserve are promoted to management positions; hiring from outside is not welcomed. Employees sign an employment contract, which stipulates, among other things, that they should not tell their colleagues about the size of their salary. An assessment and certification of personnel work is carried out, which is confidential. If an employee does not agree with this assessment, he can contact a higher manager. Employees can be members of various professional associations, where experience is exchanged. It should also be noted that

general recommendations on personnel management are given at the company level; each structural division of the company can build its own policy on human resource management.

Uzbekistan is most inclined to the European approach, but has its own peculiarities. The approach to personnel management is a combination of various elements. The emphasis is on the age of the applicant, which should not exceed 35-40 years. Large companies often hire graduates of higher education institutions with subsequent training based on training programs. Since foreign companies operate in the country, one of the requirements for hiring is knowledge of a foreign language. Since in most cases, companies consider personnel as a significant expense item, managers do not invest in personnel, pursuing a policy of hiring ready-made specialists from the labor market. Today, managers do not deny the importance of human resource management. The country has only just begun to master the experience of working with personnel, in foreign countries it has been developing for decades.

Conclusion. Personnel management is a system that consists of various functional subsystems: working conditions, labor relations, personnel registration and accounting, planning, forecasting and marketing of personnel incentives, development of personnel incentives, personnel analysis and development, development of organizational management structures. The presence of subsystems, depending on the size of the company, may vary. In small organizations, one division may perform several functions, in larger organizations one function may be performed by one structural division.

The main tasks of the personnel management system are: determining the company's need for the quantitative and qualitative composition of personnel, developing a strategic and operational plan for working with personnel, and generally ensuring the viability of the company's personnel management system. The implementation of the set tasks depends on the management methods. The most well-known management methods are administrative, economic and socio-psychological.

Administrative methods of personnel management are based on power, in the organization they have normative support for labor activity. Economic methods of personnel management are aimed at achieving a positive economic effect. The main incentive to work is wages, to which is added a developed and approved system of additional payments and allowances for personnel. Socio-psychological methods of personnel management are aimed at forming a system of relationships in the team. They are necessary for studying the needs of personnel, the interests of the individual, the group, the team as a whole.

The main mechanism that determines the management strategy in an organization is the goal-setting processes of the manager-leader. In other words, whether the manager is set up for joint activities with subordinates or prefers to decide everything independently. It is also important to note the importance of knowledge about motivation in the management activities of the organization's management interested in increasing the productivity of its employees, their full dedication to the enterprise. Understanding and applying in practice the motivation system of its employees will lead not only to a general increase in the efficiency of the organization, but also to job satisfaction of the employees themselves, an improvement in the psychological climate, and the general mood of the employees.

Thus, over the history of management, most countries have achieved heights in the field of management in various fields of activity. As world experience shows, the development of personnel management as a science has a positive impact on the activities of enterprises and organizations, and also promotes self-realization and personal development.

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